

New xanthone from the seeds of *Tectona grandis*

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A new xanthone has been isolated from the seeds of *Tectona grandis* and characterized as 1,8-dihydroxy-3,7-dimethoxy-4-*O*-[3'-methyl-4'-(3''-methyl-2''H, 5''H-2''-oxofuran-5-yl)-2-butenyl] xanthone.

Tectona grandis is mainly rich in anthraquinones^{1,2} and triterpenes³. It belongs to family *Verbenaceae* commonly known as Teak and is a useful medicinal plant⁴. The plant is generally distributed in Central India, Bengal, Maharashtra, Eastern Andhra, Deccan and Karnataka. Oil from its seeds is useful in scabies, promotes hair growth⁵, flowers in biliousness, bronchitis and urinary discharge⁶.

In continuation of our research for medicinal plants, we report, herein, isolation and structure elucidation of new xanthone derivative from *T. grandis*.

Results and discussion

Compound **1**, was shown to be xanthone by its characteristic colour reaction. It was confirmed by violet colour with magnesium and hydrochloric acid (Shinoda test)⁷. It gave positive Gibb's test⁸, which was further supported by its UV spectral⁹ and IR spectral data¹⁰.

1

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound showed three peaks for aromatic proton at δ 6.60, 7.12 and 7.65 which corresponded to 1,3,4,7,8-pentaoxygenated xanthone. It was also confirmed by its ¹³C NMR spectrum, which showed quartet at δ 63.0 (C-3) and 63.5 (C-7).

The compound on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine at RT yielded diacetyl derivative showing the presence of two hydroxy groups along with two methoxy

groups. The compound was insoluble in aqueous sodium carbonate which showed the absence of 1,3-dihydroxy system and on treatment with 10% alcoholic KOH solution and formamide, a dark red colour was developed, indicating the presence of free hydroxy group at C-1 and C-8^{11,12}. It was further supported by strong IR peaks at 1620 and 1660 cm^{-1} for doubly chelated and non-chelated carboxyl functions¹³ respectively.

Compound **1** on treatment with HI gave xanthone which on acetylation yielded triacetate. Hence one hydroxy group which was present in xanthone involved in ether linkage with some substituent. Compound **1** showed bathochromic shifts of 30 nm in band I with NaOMe, and 90 nm on treatment with HI, confirming the presence of 1,4-dihydroxy system in xanthone¹⁴ and also support that the substituent must be attached to the 4-position of xanthone.

A doublet of two protons δ 5.00 was assigned to $-\text{OCH}_2-$ group at C-1', the methine protons appeared as a multiplet at δ 5.72 and the 4'-methylene group was observed as a multiplet at δ 2.35.

The multiplet centered at δ 4.90 was assigned to the proton at C-5'' of a five membered lactone. The triplet at δ 1.90 for three protons could be assigned to the methyl function at the α -position of the α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone group. The three methyl protons at C-5' appeared as a broad singlet at δ 1.80. The size and nature of the side chain was also assessed by a study of its mass spectrum¹⁴. Thus compound **1** was identified as 1,8-dihydroxy-3,7-dimethoxy-4-*O*-[3'-methyl-4'-(3''-methyl-2''H, 5''H-2''-oxofuran-5-yl)-2-butenyl] xanthone.

The proposed structure of **1** was confirmed by ¹³C NMR and decoupling experiments. The relationship of H-6'' with H-4'' and H-5'' was established by decoupling experiment. Irradiation at δ 1.8866 caused the multiplet at δ 6.93 (H-4, dq) to change to a doublet accompanied by a simultaneous

change in the shape of the multiplet at δ 4.90 (m, H-5''). Irradiation at δ 2.3648 simplified the multiplets at δ 6.93 (H-4'') and 4.90 (H-5'') establishing the relationship between H-4', H-4'' and H-5''. This was further supported by the appearance of sharp singlet at δ 1.90 (H-6''), a dd at δ 2.35 (H-4') and simplification of the multiplet at δ 6.93 (H-4'') on irradiation at δ 4.9254. Irradiation at 5.0416 simplified the multiplet at δ 5.72 (H-2') showing the relationship between H-1' and H-2' supported by the change of doublet at δ 5.00 (H-1') on irradiation at δ 5.7267. Irradiation of δ 6.9342 changed the dd appearing like a triplet at δ 1.90 (H-6'') to a doublet accompanied by a simultaneous change in the shape of the multiplet at δ 4.90 (H-5'')¹⁵.

Experimental

The seeds of *T. grandis* were collected from Rajnandgaon, Madhya Pradesh, India. A herbarium specimen was preserved in Botanical Survey of India, Allahabad (sheet No. 47818). M.ps. measured in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. UV and IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Beckman-DK2 spectrophotometer and Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, respectively. ¹H NMR (200 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz) spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker-300A spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL-JMS-DX 300 mass spectrophotometer.

The air-dried and finely crushed seeds (3 kg) were extracted with boiling ethanol and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. It was separated by flash column chromatography on silica gel, 60 (Merck 24398) using different organic solvents of increasing polarity. The compound was isolated from chloroform : ethyl acetate (2 : 8, v/v) fraction as light yellow crystal (350 mg), m.p. 265° (Found : C, 66.37; H, 5.30. C₂₅H₂₄O₉ calcd. for : C, 66.10; H, 5.01%); homogenous on TLC R_f 0.63; ν_{\max} 3340 br (chelated hydroxyl), 1670, 1640, 1610 and 1580 cm⁻¹ (chelated unsaturated carbonyl; suggesting the presence of a xanthone skeleton)¹⁰; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 235, 265, 315, 340, 400; +AlCl₃ 236, 278, 325, 385 nm; NMR δ_{H} (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) δ 6.60 (1H, s), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.12 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 3.82 (3H, s), 3.92 (3H, s), 5.00 (2H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 5.70 (1H, m, *J* 6.6 and 0.98 Hz), 2.35 (2H, m, *J* 6.5 Hz), 1.80 (3H, br s), 6.93 (1H, dq, *J* 1.70 and 0.96 Hz), 4.90 (1H, m,

J 6.5 and 1.95 Hz) and 1.90 (3H, t); δ_{C} (CDCl₃, 75.5 MHz) 184.0 (C-9), 174.0 (C-2''), 169.0 (C-1), 161.0 (C-3), 160.0 (C-7), 157.0 (C-8), 148.2 (C-4), 145.3 (C-4a), 144.3 (C-4''), 142.1 (C-4b), 137.0 (C-3'), 130.8 (C-3''), 124.0 (C-2'), 105.0 (C-8a and C-8b), 102.0 (C-6), 100.0 (C-5), 98.4 (C-2), 79.60 (C-5''), 70.0 (C-1'), 63.5 (-OCH₃), 63.0 (-OCH₃), 43.37 (C-4'), 17.24 (C-6''), 11.0 (C-5'); *m/z* 468 (M⁺), 371, 304, 276, 165, 97, 69, 41.

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